

Research

Temporal annual and seasonal NDVI variation of Sagarmatha national park, Nepal and its relationship with precipitation and soil moisture

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Abstract: The researches related to the national parks are important for detecting changes, managing and protecting resources in them. The vegetation change study is more vital as vegetation is the part of every ecosystems and functioning of the park. There had been limited study regarding vegetation changes and impact of climatic and environmental factor on greenery in Nepal. To fill this gap, our study applied satellite based NDVI, precipitation and soil moisture data to inspect changes in vegetation and their relation with climatic variables in Sagarmatha National Park (SNP). Our study revealed that the greenery contributors, forests, shrubs, grasslands and agricultural lands had increased during period of 2000-2018. These changes was due to reverse effect of both precipitation and soil moisture. In light of these findings, we assured that the greenery of the park was well preserved during these 18 years. Our research provided ecological and social implication for the SNP region as plan and polices regarding wellbeing of both vegetation and local dwellers could be formulated based on vegetation condition of park.

Keywords: NDVI, National Park, Annual, Seasonal, Precipitation, Soil moisture

Introduction

The protected areas of Himalayas provide ecological changes on change of anthropogenic activities and climate impacts on vegetation. The protected areas in high mountains have supported

all sorts of biomes because of the rapid change in elevation within a small range [1]. The climate change have created a serious ecological deterioration in such biomes causing serious impact in vegetation [2,3]. In addition, these protected areas are highly subjected to deforestation, over-grazing, cultivation of marginal soils, management systems, and mismanaged tourism [4,5]. The sharp increase in the elevation in the mountains is advantageous for studying climate change impact over various sorts of greenery types [6,7]. These areas are also appealing for studies on the vegetation and climate change [8].

The study of vegetation changes provides a vital information about relation between climate change and terrestrial ecosystem. Satellite based remote sensing has become conceivable acquisition for ecological research for visualizing and simulating change in vegetation over the large scale [9]. Satellite or remote sensed data such as Normalized vegetation index (NDVI), being burning topic within the climate change research field [10], had proved it's a successful prototype of vegetation activities [11-13]. NDVI is based on differences in pigment absorption features from red and near-infrared reflectance [14]. The value of NDVI ranges from -1.0 to 1.0 , increasing positive NDVI values indicated increasing greenery of the region. NDVI provided quantitative representation of the area of interest by classifying it into land cover classes and its application in local, regional, and global scales [15]. The spatiotemporal variation in climate change and eco environment conditions among different region entangled the effect of environmental change in vegetation activity [16].

The linkage between NDVI and precipitation highlights precipitation effect over greenery of vegetation. Precipitation is the one of major contributor along with for affecting growth of vegetation [17]. The global analysis of NDVI with precipitation showed no significant correlation with precipitation [18]. The NDVI is found to be negatively correlated with precipitation in the Northern Hemisphere [19]. In Nepal ,the precipitation had a negative impact over NDVI annually and most of the seasons except in winter and post- monsoon seasons where the correlation was slightly positive [20]. There was a significant increasing trend in the warm-season NDVI over the Koshi River Basin for 1982–2006 [21]. NDVI trends and correlations with precipitation from a nearby meteorological station of Manaslu conservation area were computed for 2000–2008 [22]. There are many works considering respond of vegetation to rainfall [23,24], while fewer showed linkage of soil moisture and greenery [25,26]. The study of NDVI and precipitation trend exists in

Nepal but until now, no study had been done for soil moisture-vegetation correlation or both factors simultaneously.

In this study, we tended to deduce mean annual and seasonal trend of NDVI from 2000-2017 for Sagarmatha National Park, Nepal. The vegetation type was also classified into four categories; Forest, Shrub, Agricultural and Grassland to represent trends and greenery change for individual vegetation types for park. The seasonal and annual trends of NDVI were correlated with precipitation and soil moisture to observe their effects for vegetation change. The aim of this study was to highlight the greenery change in Nepal's first national park that was inscribed as a Natural World Heritage Site. The study provided changes on vegetation of park that could be fruitful to inscribe plans and policies regarding preservation and protection of greenery.

Material and Method

Study Area

Sagarmatha national park, "Top of the world", as named by UNESCO, is an 1148 km² national park situated in the Himalayan ecological zone in Khumbu region [27]. The elevation of the park ranges from 2845 m to 8848 m at summit of Mount Everest. The majority of the parks area (69 percent) is over 5000 m, which is barren and snow covered and rest of the land area, 28% is grazing land and nearly 3% is forested [28] (Figure 1). The steep slopes below 6000m are intact as forest and grassland, whereas areas with relatively gentle slopes are cultivable land [29]. The majority of the park area lies within the elevation classes of 4000-5000m (31%) and 5000-6000m (52%) [30]. The greenery change of the park was more clearer on elevation 3000-4000 m, where forest have decreased and shrubs have increased between period of 1992 – 2006 [31]. The land cover change of park showed region have suffered extensive loss on snow cover and glacier melt with degrading forest and agricultural area and uplifted portion of grazing land, shrubs and settlement [29]. Though the area had been continuous observed for change in glacier cover [32], there had been little study about the greenery change of the park [33].

Figure 1 : Map of Sagarmatha national park with map of Nepal (left) showing boundary of park with its land cover types (right)

Methods

The temporal annual and seasonal trend in NDVI, precipitation and soil moisture was calculated using linear regression. The season was classified as winter (December, January, February), Pre-monsoon (March, April, May), Monsoon (June, July, August, September) and post monsoon (October, November). The linear approach detected the potential change in the time series patterns where the positive slope indicated an increasing trend, and a negative slope showed a decreasing trend [34]. Equation (1) showed the general form of linear equation to determine trend in NDVI and climatic variables.

$$y = a + bt + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Here, y represented the monthly or climatic variable of NDVI, t was the time, a and b were fitted variables (a was the intercept, b was the trend), and the residual error was ϵ . The slope of this linear equation was calculated using equation 2.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n i \cdot \text{NDVI}_i - \sum_{i=1}^n i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \text{NDVI}_i}{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n i)^2} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Here, n was the number of years in the study period; i was the year and *Slope* was the trend of vegetation dynamics.

The technique of Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) was applied to determine strength of NDVI with climatic parameters. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) also referred to as the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was a measure of the linear correlation between two variables X and Y . It had a value between +1 and -1, where 1 is total positive linear correlation, 0 is no linear correlation, and -1 is total negative linear correlation. If the correlation value ‘ r ’ between the two variables is positive with the p -value less than 0.05, the correlation is statistically significant. The correlation was calculated for annual NDVI with precipitation and soil moisture for same season and preceding season.

The NDVI of SNP was arranged based on Greenery contributor types; Forest, shrub land, Grassland and Agricultural area based on ICIMOD land cover dataset (Figure 2). The annual mean, trend and greenery ratio change (GCR) for annual and seasonal change NDVI was calculated for period 2000 – 2017. Eqn (3) calculated the value of *GCR* for studied number of years (N) for Mean NDVI (*MEAN*), with linear regression slope (s).

$$\text{GCR} = \left(\frac{\text{MEAN}}{s} \right) * N * 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Datasets

The monthly NDVI data were generated from bi-monthly data using Terra Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectro-radiometer (MODIS) Vegetation Indices (MOD13Q1) Version 6 data generated at the 250-meter spatial resolution as a Level 3 product [35]. The precipitation dataset ERA-5 was the global reanalysis dataset, which provided global, hourly estimates of atmospheric variables, at a horizontal resolution of 31 km and 137 vertical levels from the surface to 0.01 hPa. The datasets contained numerous atmospheric, land and oceanic variable an approximately 30km

spatial resolution and are available at multiple temporal resolutions [36]. The climate change initiative (CCI) soil moisture data was available from 1979-present at 0.25° spatial resolution and daily temporal resolution, which we aggregated to monthly and seasonal time-steps (9 and 3 month) [37].

Results

Trend and inter annual variation in seasonal NDVI

The annual trend of NDVI escalated significantly at the rate of 0.001 year⁻¹ (p=0.02, R= 0.54). The mean and deviation of annual NDVI from 2000-2017 is 0.09 and ±0.01 respectively (Figure 2). The trend of NDVI was positive for all seasons. The monsoon season NDVI had significantly increased at the rate of 0.002 year⁻¹ (R =0.7, p = 0.001), while the trend were positive but insignificant for winter, pre monsoon and post monsoon seasons. The mean NDVI value of winter, pre monsoon and post monsoon were 0.06, 0.08 and 0.10 respectively. As compared to other season, monsoon season had highest mean value of 0.11±0.01. The insignificant trend of winter, pre monsoon and post monsoon NDVI were 0.001, 0.0008 and 0.0007 per year respectively. Among the four season monsoon had the largest total increase with annual increase of 0.002 yr⁻¹ and pre monsoon NDVI with least increase of 0.0008 yr⁻¹.

Figure 2 : Mean (a) annual (b) winter (c) Pre-monsoon (d) Monsoon and (e) Post- monsoon NDVI trend of Sagarmatha National park for period 2000-2017

Zonal Trend in NDVI

All contributors had positive GCR and trend annually, with trend of NDVI in forest was highest (0.00217 per year) and lowest on shrub lines (0.00107 per year) (Table 1). The forest were major contributor for annual greenery of park as the mean value of NDVI is 0.485 with relative increase of 8.053%. Annually the grassland had higher greenery growth of 11.127%. The mean NDVI for all season was highest for forest and least for grassland. The highest mean NDVI value was of forest in post-monsoon (0.564) and lowest mean was for grassland in winter (0.186). The general pattern of mean NDVI value from highest to lowest is forest, agriculture, shrub land and grass land. The pattern slightly altered for post monsoon as mean NDVI value of shrub land is more than that of agricultural area. All regions had positive change in NDVI for all season expect for agricultural area with decreasing trend of -0.00025 yr^{-1} during post monsoon. Astonishingly, the most positive trend of 0.00422 yr^{-1} was also for farming area for winter season. The result

showed greenery growth for all season except for only negative GCR is for agricultural region with change -1.382 % during post monsoon season. The greenery change ratio for winter season for grassland and agriculture were highest with a value of 33.29% and 29.32% respectively. The change showed that the grasslands are increasing by high ratio every season. The monsoon trend in agriculture growth was also low value of 0.393%.

Table 1 : Zonal distribution of vegetation with their slope change (trend), annual mean value and Greenery change ratio (in percentage)

Season	Vegetation Type	Slope	Annual mean	Relative trend (%)
Annual	Forest	0.00217	0.485	8.053
	Shrub land	0.00107	0.306	6.294
	Grassland	0.00136	0.220	11.127
	Agriculture	0.00146	0.335	7.844
Winter	Forest	0.00142	0.458	5.580
	Shrub land	0.00117	0.255	8.258
	Grassland	0.00344	0.186	33.290
	Agriculture	0.00422	0.259	29.328
Pre-monsoon	Forest	0.00189	0.472	7.207
	Shrub land	0.00034	0.275	2.161
	Grassland	0.00069	0.188	6.620
	Agriculture	0.00108	0.293	6.634
Monsoon	Forest	0.00313	0.482	11.688
	Shrub land	0.00137	0.353	6.985
	Grassland	0.00146	0.259	10.146
	Agriculture	0.00009	0.425	0.393
Post-monsoon	Forest	0.00111	0.564	3.542
	Shrub land	0.00140	0.354	7.118
	Grassland	0.00059	0.254	4.241
	Agriculture	-0.00025	0.336	-1.382

Relationship of NDVI with Precipitation and Soil moisture

The annual and seasonal correlation between NDVI and precipitation showed negative characteristics i.e. increase in precipitation decreased greenness of the park. The correlation was significant and strongly correlated on winter ($R = -0.74, p = 0.0003$) and post monsoon ($R = -0.71, p = 0.0008$). The relation were weakly correlated and insignificant for annual, pre monsoon and monsoon periods. Similarly, soil moisture also seemed to hamper the growth of NDVI, as correlation was negative for annual and seasonal scale. There was strong and significant correlation for monsoon NDVI and soil moisture ($R = -0.76, p = 0.0002$). However, for annual scale and rest of the season the correlation was weak and insignificant. The lag correlation with preceding season failed to show any sort of significance of precipitation and soil moisture with NDVI.

Table 2 : Correlation table of annual, winter, pre monsoon, monsoon and post monsoon NDVI changes with precipitation (R_{P-NDVI}) and soil moisture (R_{S-NDVI}). Correlation were represented for lag for preceding season and post season. Significant correlation were represented marked by ‘*’.

Seasons	Correlation coefficient R_{P-NDVI}		Correlation coefficient R_{S-NDVI}	
	Same season	Preceding season	Same season	Preceding season
Winter	-0.74* (0.0003)	0.20 (0.41)	-0.13 (0.58)	-0.17 (0.49)
Pre monsoon	-0.34 (0.16)	-0.37 (0.12)	-0.42 (0.08)	0.01 (0.95)
Monsoon	-0.32 (0.18)	0.03 (0.90)	-0.76* (0.0002)	-0.06 (0.80)
Post monsoon	-0.71* (0.0008)	-0.11 (0.65)	-0.11 (0.65)	0.07 (0.77)
Annual	-0.20 (0.40)		-0.35 (0.14)	

Discussion

Our result showed that the NDVI of SNP had increased for period of 2000-2017. NDVI was found to be increasing globally, including India and Southeast China during 1982-2012 [38] and a coherent result was seen in Tibetan plateau during 2000 to 2009 [21]. The result of SNP was consistent with various research on Northern hemisphere, which showed positive trend in NDVI [9,19,39]. The NDVI of whole Nepal along with mountainous region ascended during period of 1982-2015 [20]. A recent study in Koshi Basin had also revealed a small increase in NDVI in the central Himalaya region [21]. However, our study was limited to only alpine region, which represented very small fragment of vegetation in Nepal. The park consisted of high percentage of snow cover and barren land; there was low value of NDVI for national park on Himalayan region. The ecological supportive phenomenon such as restoration and facilitation could be responsible on grooming greenery of SNP. The successful recruitment and establishment can lead to a lower mortality [40]. The implementation of vegetation protection legal frameworks have also uplifted the greenery of protected area of Nepal [41].

The greenery contributor in SNP: forest, shrubs, grasslands and agriculture crops had increased during 2000- 2018. The conservation programs like Community Forestry Program (CFP) had been effective forest management strategy to contribute biodiversity protection and minimize carbon production [42]. This moisture driven shrub growth was stabilized by facilitation in high altitudes [43]. This facilitation could be cause of shrubs growth on SNP, which is also located in high altitude. Tourism had also played important role on change of greenery on SNP. Tourism has become very important for local development in national parks of Nepal [44]. This caused significant decrease in cattle rearing and grazing activities as farmers and shepherds are rather involved in tourism rather than cattle rearing [45]. This lead to increase in land covered in grass, which explained huge rise of greenery in grassland throughout every season. In addition, the warming in global scale had been affecting glaciers and snow covers in high mountains [46]. This had resulted on melting of ice and snow and exposure of rocks, which left more space for greenery facilitation. The high increase in agriculture area in the park was due to growing settlements as there was high flow of number of local residences and outsiders [29]. However, the farming and crop production had decreased during post monsoon. The rainfall intensity decreased as the season shifts from monsoon to post monsoon period [47]. This decrease might have degraded agricultural products, as it requires more water for facilitation of cropland.

The precipitation had a vegetative impact on growth of vegetation. Recent study in Nepal also highlighted there was a negative correlation between NDVI and precipitation in most of the regions [20]. The negative trend of NDVI with precipitation was observed on different global [48] and regional study [49]. However, In central Himalayas the radial growth of shrubs were driven by growing-season precipitation [50]. There might be lag effect of precipitation, which may affect vegetation growth in proceeding months or seasons [51]. Our result also highlighted this effect but correlation were not strong and significant. The soil moisture also yielded negative with NDVI of the SNP. The consistency of remotely sensed soil moisture decreased with increasing vegetation cover [52]. The rainfall is major factor on determining scale of soil moisture [53]. Therefore, they both have similar impact over NDVI change in the park. The time lag effect of climatic factors was the most important factor in determining greenery productivity in central Himalayas[22]. This might be the reason of negative correlation of NDVI with both precipitation and soil moisture. However, the lag correlation also failed to show any sorts of significant results regarding the climate-vegetation relation. Therefore, the changes in vegetation might be more related to other environmental variables like temperature and CO₂ variation [20].

Conclusion

The vegetation of the SNP increased during 2000-2017. The greenery rate of forests, shrubs, grasslands and agriculture lands uplifted for 18 years. The precipitation and soil moisture had negative impact over vegetation expansion as they had not contributing well in increasing greenery. There was not any significant contribution of preceding season climates towards vegetation. The precipitation of winter and post monsoon had negative impact towards vegetation and monsoon soil moisture showed similar effect on greenery. However, the impact of temperature and monthly lags correlation can be used in further studies to observe connection between vegetation and climate shifts. As a concluding remark, the good policies and frameworks in the park have improved vegetation coverage in a protected area.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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